

Experiment Design for Data Science - Group 38 - The Unfairness of Popularity Bias in Music Recommendation: A Reproducibility Study

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ABSTRACT

A reproducibility study which aimed to investigate findings regarding recommender system bias in the movie domain for songs has been chosen to be reproduced. The challenges of setting up a suitable environment for the reproduction of the obtained results was non-trivial due to unclear versioning and partly undocumented data pre-processing steps. The original analysis performed by the analyzed authors was verified further by using cross validation for significance testing and reconstructing the describe data sampling approach. The findings described in the analyzed publication were successfully validated and reproduced.

KEYWORDS

reproducibility, recommender systems, music recommendation

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1 CONTEXT OF THIS PAPER

This project was performed as a part of a the lecture "Experiment Design for Data Science" at the Technical University of Vienna (TU Wien). The goal of this project is the investigate the reproducibility of a specific publication.

2 OVERVIEW

The publication analyzed by our group describes a reproducibility study itself. The original paper, which it aims to reproduce, is concerned with bias in recommender systems. More specifically it looks at recommender systems in the movie domain. The analyzed study tries to reproduce the study results in the domain of music recommendation. The analyzed phenomenon of popularity bias entails the fact that popular items get a lot more exposure than less popular items when common recommender systems try to predict new items for users.

The original publication is called **original paper** in the following section while the publication our group was tasked with investigating is referred to as **analyzed paper**. Their authors are referred to as **original authors** and **analyzed authors** respectively.

In the following parts we reproduce the findings of the analyzed paper and also investigate how the analyzed paper reproduces the original paper.

3 THE ORIGINAL PAPER [1]

The original paper investigated recommendation bias towards popular items from a user perspective. Meaning how recommender systems tend to more often predict popular items than unpopular items contradictory to the user's preference and expectations. The authors used the MovieLens 1M[2] dataset containing movie rating of approximately 3.9k movies by over 6k users. Given this data movies are recommended for a specific user. For the experiments all users were ranked by the ratio of popular items in their profile. Based on this list the users were divided into 3 groups: Niche users are 20% bottom, blockbuster-focused users the 20% top and diverse users all other users of this ranked list.

The original author's experiment results show that many recommender systems are biased towards recommending popular items even if a user's history suggests their interest in exclusively non-popular items. To perform their experiments they used User KNN, Item KNN, SVD++, Biased Matrix factorization as well as simple Most popular and Random recommendation algorithms. For better comparison they tuned these algorithms to achieve a similar precision.

4 THE ANALYZED PAPER [3]

The analyzed paper aims to reproduce the observed bias of the original paper in the domain of music recommendation. The analyzed authors used the LFM-1b dataset[4], a dataset containing the listening history for over 120k users of the LastFM music platform. The dataset contains user artist interactions which are used to predict the preference of a specific user for a specific artist. In contrast, the recommended items in the original paper are movies not actors or film markers or any other entity that is related to more than one item. It is therefore debatable if music tracks as recommendation items would not be the more adequate choice to translate the original paper into the music domain.

The users were divided into three groups by selecting the 1000 top, 1000 bottom and 1000 users closest to the median as ordered by their preferences to listen mainstream music. The mainstream metric is a pre-calculated feature of the LFM-1b dataset. For their experiments the analyzed authors use the same algorithms as in the original paper but excluded ItemKNN and SVD++ to reduce computational effort. The default parameters of the Surprise toolkit[5] for all algorithms were used which stays in contrast to the original paper. The results showed that users of the bottom mainstream music listeners group receive worse recommendations than users from the top mainstream music listeners group.

5 THE REPRODUCIBILITY ANALYSIS

The following section describes our steps taken to and findings found while reproducing the analyzed paper.

5.1 Available resources

We found and used the following resources to reproduce the analyzed paper:

- The GitHub repository containing the analyzed authors' published code.[6]
- A Zendo entry[7] for the used user groups and user artist interactions of the analyzed paper
- The LFM_1b dataset[4] provided by the Johannes Kepler University (JKU) Linz
- A referenced paper[8] defining different mainstreamness scores

5.2 Performed steps

We used the Jupyter notebooks provided on GitHub by the analyzed authors to rerun their calculations. Since they only provided a list of used package without explicit package versions, we tried to reconstruct which versions were most likely used. The analyzed paper was submitted on the 10th of December 2019. All versions of the required libraries were chosen to correspond to the latest stable version at this date. As python 3.8.0 was the latest major python release by the time the paper was submitted[9] this version was chosen.

The versions of all libraries obtained are noted in the GitHub repository associated with this project [10]

With the Jupyter notebooks, external dependencies and the pre-processed data of the author provided on Zenodo we were able to execute the analyzed authors code. These numeric results as well as the generated plots were identical to the ones presented by the authors in their paper.

The first thing we noticed is that the sampling in the analyzed paper differs from the original paper. As described, above the analyzed authors order the users by mainstreamness and took the top 1000 user for the High Mainstreamness Group (HighMS), the bottom 1000 users for the Low Mainstreamness Group (LowMS) and the 1000 users closest to the median for the Medium Mainstreamness Group (MedMS). In contrast, in the original paper the three groups were sampled as the top 20%, bottom 20% of most popular items for HighMS and LowMS and all other items for the MedMS group. Therefore the low and the high group in the original paper contain much less extreme items than in the analyzed paper. Considering that the top 1000 users with the highest mainstreamness score only reflect the 0.8% most extreme mainstream listeners, while the corresponding group in the original paper features the top 20% most extreme items, a significant reduction in diversity takes place.

We argue that this extreme sampling could influence the observed bias effect in the outcome for the low and high group and thus do not reflect the same procedure as presented in the original paper. Due to this, we investigated a different sampling strategy:

We split all 120k users of the LFM_1b dataset into three groups according the `mainstreamness_global` (the 20% top, 20% bottom and the rest of all users). 1000 users were than randomly sampled from each group. With this sampling we re-executed the given

data pipeline. Figure 1 shows the resulting Δ GAP comparison plot obtained by using the sampling approach described above.

5.3 Comparison of results

Figure 1: Δ GAP results for initial user group segmentation

Figure 2: Δ GAP results for from the analyzed paper

When comparing the result obtained by our initial recreation attempt to the corresponding plot from the analyzed paper in Figure 4 it is apparent that there are large differences in the user group segmentation which affect the outcome significantly. The segmentation approach used in the analyzed paper seems to lead to a higher Δ GAP for the Most Popular algorithm compared to our segmentation.

However, further investigations revealed that we were not working with the exact same data as the paper authors. The user with the highest mainstreamness score in the Last-FM dataset was not the same user as given in the papers data files. Furthermore, querying the Last-FM dataset for specific users, revealed that the authors used not the same value for mainstreamness as given in the Last-FM dataset. Which is contrary to what is stated in the paper:

"[...] we use the mainstreamness score, which is available for the users in the LFM-1b dataset and which is defined as the overlap between a user's listening history and the aggregated listening history of all Last.fm users in the dataset."

Also the metadata of the provided user group files described the value column as `mainstreamness_value`. Only in the datafile

itself the column was named `M_global_R_APC`, which intensified our suspicion that a transformed or different value than the Last-FM dataset mainstreamness has been used. We contacted the authors and learned that they indeed did not use the `mainstreamness_global` from the LFM_1b dataset but instead used the `M_global_R_APC` definition as proposed by Bauer et. al[4].

5.4 Reproducing the calculation of `M_global_R_APC`

In order to execute our adapted sampling and to reproduce the metric calculation we started to implement the `M_global_R_APC` value as defined in this paper and stated in Equation 1.

$$M_{R,APC}^{global}(u) = \tau(\text{ranks}(APC), \text{ranks}(APC(u))) \quad (1)$$

This metric defines mainstreamness of a specific user’s music history by Kendall’s correlation of all artists ranked by the total play counts and the artists listened by the user and ranked by the users play counts. With the implementation of this metric we were able to calculate the exact same value for a given user as provided group data files of the analyzed paper, which in theory enabled us to execute our adapted sampling strategy. However, we were not able to come up with an appropriate vectorized version of the `M_global_R_APC`. Our implementation requires about 10s per user to calculate this metric on the hardware available to us personally, which is infeasible for 120k users given our time and resource budget. We concluded that the authors either executed this calculation on a high performance cluster or implemented the calculation in a vectorized fashion to speed up execution.

5.5 Reproducing Model Validation and Statistical Testing

In the analyzed paper the authors claim that the NMF model yields the best result (i.e. lowest *MAE*). They also claim that the differences in model performance on the different parts of the dataset (LowMS, MedMS, HighMS, All) are statistically significant according to a t-test with $p < 0.005$.

By just looking at Table 1 in the analyzed paper it is unclear which type of t-test has been performed and which means have been compared. In order to validate the analyzed authors reported results we tried to reproduce the model validation as well as the statistical tests.

To validate the model performances measured we used the code provided by the authors and adapted it slightly to get additional information such as the raw predictions from the different models for further analysis.

mae_all	mae_low	mae_med	mae_high	algo
38.561220	42.948022	33.900131	40.686397	UserItemAvg
45.632008	49.759900	42.483605	45.991037	UserKNN
41.884150	46.580840	37.585348	43.242634	UserKNNAvg
34.879921	38.422262	30.596328	37.285075	NMF

Table 1: Model performance using *MAE* as performance metric

As can be seen in Table 1 the NMF model indeed feature the lowest *MAE* on all parts of the data. However, the results are not entirely robust since only a single train/test split has been used which means that the effect on sampling imbalances cannot be discarded. Therefore, we investigate this problem further in the next section using cross-validation.

In the second step we performed the statistical tests as described in the available Jupyter notebook. The only t-test that been performed is a two sample t-test using the prediction errors on the LowMS and HighMS users. It doesn’t seem like any tests have been performed regarding the MedMS users.

t Statistic	p Value	Algorithm
-6.410088	1.457457e-10	UserItemAvg
-10.222608	1.591726e-24	UserKNN
-9.298158	1.442191e-20	UserKNNAvg
-2.812836	4.911127e-03	NMF

Table 2: Two sample t-test *MAE* high vs. *MAE* low for each algorithm

In Table 2 the results for the first t-test can be found. The p values featured in the table indicated that the differences are highly significant (i.e. all p values are < 0.05).

t Statistic	p Value	Algorithm
22.929584	3.103631e-116	UserItemAvg
11.444310	2.554827e-30	UserKNN
18.746801	2.326156e-78	UserKNNAvg
19.749972	9.343993e-87	NMF

Table 3: Two sample t-test *MAE* high vs. *MAE* medium for each algorithm

t Statistic	p Value	Algorithm
-29.358120	4.041204e-189	UserItemAvg
-22.710111	4.682693e-114	UserKNN
-28.603068	1.225187e-179	UserKNNAvg
-22.499055	5.522408e-112	NMF

Table 4: Two sample t-test *MAE* medium vs. *MAE* low for each algorithm

In addition we also performed two sample t-test for all other user groups as can be seen in Table 3 and Table 4. All p values are < 0.05 and therefore significant.

5.6 Additional Statistical Testing

As mentioned before the model validation has only been performed using one train test split. To improve the significance of the results we performed 5-fold cross-validation.

algo	mae_all	mae_low	mae_med	mae_high
NMF	34.826228	38.251262	30.819504	36.966665
UserItemAvg	38.597781	42.901547	34.188141	40.458539
UserKNN	45.670528	49.491061	42.900413	45.805219
UserKNNAvg	41.951480	46.484833	37.940609	43.071083

Table 5: Model performance using MAE as performance metric

Table 5 shows the mean model performance using cross-validation. The NMF is still the best performing model for all user groups. To show that the results are indeed significant with $\alpha = 0.05$ we performed the same statistical tests as before (i.e. two sample t-test).

t Statistic	p Value	Algorithm
-15.676295	2.229392e-55	UserItemAvg
-22.666401	1.024629e-113	UserKNN
-21.540912	6.786349e-103	UserKNNAvg
-7.193133	6.336360e-13	NMF

Table 6: Two sample t-test MAE high vs. MAE low for each algorithm using cross validation results

t Statistic	p Value	Algorithm
47.337713	0.000000e+00	UserItemAvg
21.211420	7.801148e-100	UserKNN
38.031295	0.000000e+00	UserKNNAvg
40.644507	0.000000e+00	NMF

Table 7: Two sample t-test MAE high vs. MAE medium for each algorithm using cross validation results

t Statistic	p Value	Algorithm
-63.123592	0.0	UserItemAvg
-46.030867	0.0	UserKNN
-60.765132	0.0	UserKNNAvg
-47.696417	0.0	NMF

Table 8: Two sample t-test MAE medium vs. MAE low for each algorithm using cross validation results

As can be seen in Table 6, 7, 8 the results are indeed significant with p values well below 0.05. To show that the performance differences between the NMF and all other models are significant we performed paired sample t-tests using the crossvalidation results.

Table 9 shows the results of the paired t-tests. The p values are all exactly zero which might seem odd but this underlines the significance of the results even more since this means that the null hypothesis is entirely infeasible. Lastly, we looked at the variance of the different models as can be seen in Figure 3 and 4.

t Statistic	p Value	Algorithm	Dataset
-88.080805	0.0	UserItemAvg	low
-92.817506	0.0	UserItemAvg	med
-71.221515	0.0	UserItemAvg	high
-145.436214	0.0	UserItemAvg	all
-185.467541	0.0	UserKNN	low
-256.779993	0.0	UserKNN	med
-161.269761	0.0	UserKNN	high
-351.666213	0.0	UserKNN	all
-134.412910	0.0	UserKNNAvg	low
-168.504432	0.0	UserKNNAvg	med
-113.566081	0.0	UserKNNAvg	high
-240.907508	0.0	UserKNNAvg	all

Table 9: Paired sample t-test of all algorithms considering different parts of the data

Figure 3: Boxplots representing the MAE of a specific Algorithm for different parts of the data

In Figure 3 we visualized the results as box plots for each model for the different user groups. The overall variance of the models seems to be very low.

Figure 4: Change in MAE per fold for different parts of the data

This can also be seen when looking at the lines of Figure 4. There are very little fluctuations between the different folds. The strongest fluctuations can be observed for the HighMS user group.

6 CONCLUSION

This reproducibility attempts performed in the scope of this project were largely successfully. Significance testing performed by the analyzed authors held true when cross validation was used to extend it. Our group faced challenging in setting up the environment used by the analyzed authors, however. The main reasons for this was ambiguous versions for the libraries used as well largely undocumented steps needed to engineer the dataset used in the publication.

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